

Smarandache's Cevians Theorem (II)

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Abstract.

In this paper we present the Smarandache's Cevians Theorem (II) in the geometry of the triangle.

Smarandache's Cevians Theorem (II)

In a triangle ΔABC we draw the Cevians AA_1 , BB_1 , CC_1 that intersect in P . Then:

$$\frac{PA}{PA_1} \cdot \frac{PB}{PB_1} \cdot \frac{PC}{PC_1} = \frac{AB \cdot BC \cdot CA}{A_1B \cdot B_1C \cdot C_1A}$$

Solution 6.

In the triangle ΔABC we apply the Ceva's theorem:

$$AC_1 \cdot BA_1 \cdot CB_1 = -AB_1 \cdot CA_1 \cdot BC_1 \tag{1}$$

In the triangle ΔAA_1B , cut by the transversal CC_1 , we'll apply the Menelaus' theorem:

$$AC_1 \cdot BC \cdot A_1P = AP \cdot A_1C \cdot BC_1 \tag{2}$$

In the triangle ΔBB_1C , cut by the transversal AA_1 , we apply again the Menelaus' theorem:

$$BA_1 \cdot CA \cdot B_1P = BP \cdot B_1A \cdot CA_1 \tag{3}$$

We apply one more time the Menelaus' theorem in the triangle ΔCC_1A cut by the transversal BB_1 :

$$AB \cdot C_1P \cdot CB_1 = AB_1 \cdot CP \cdot C_1B \tag{4}$$

We divide each relation (2), (3), and (4) by relation (1), and we obtain:

$$\frac{PA}{PA_1} = \frac{BC}{BA_1} \cdot \frac{B_1A}{B_1C} \tag{5}$$

$$\frac{PB}{PB_1} = \frac{CA}{CB_1} \cdot \frac{C_1B}{C_1A} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{PC}{PC_1} = \frac{AB}{AC_1} \cdot \frac{A_1C}{A_1B} \quad (7)$$

Multiplying (5) by (6) and by (7), we have:

$$\frac{PA}{PA_1} \cdot \frac{PB}{PB_1} \cdot \frac{PC}{PC_1} = \frac{AB \cdot BC \cdot CA}{A_1B \cdot B_1C \cdot C_1A} \cdot \frac{AB_1 \cdot BC_1 \cdot CA_1}{A_1B \cdot B_1C \cdot C_1A}$$

but the last fraction is equal to 1 in conformity to Ceva's theorem.

Unsolved Problem related to the Smarandache's Cevians Theorem (II).

Is it possible to generalize this problem for a polygon?

References:

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- [2] F. Smarandache, *Eight Solved and Eight Open Problems in Elementary Geometry*, in arXiv.org, Cornell University, NY, USA.
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